

Incidence of Home Accidents and the Prevalence of Burns and Fractures among Geriatric Patients in Selected Public Hospitals in Southwest Nigeria

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the incidence of home accidents and to quantify the prevalence of burns and fractures in geriatric patients. A cross-sectional analysis was conducted on geriatric patients aged 65 years and older who were admitted due to home-related accidents. Participants were selected through stratified random sampling from selected public hospitals in Southwest Nigeria. A sample of 134 participants was randomly selected for the study using the minimum sample size formula developed by Cochran as determinant. Data were collected on demographics, prevalence and knowledge of the causes and preventive strategies of home accidents. Inferential statistics were employed, specifically Independent t-test, to determine the strength and direction of associations. There is relatively high knowledge of causes and preventive strategies of home accident burns and fractures, yet many respondents still lacks some appropriate home modifications that can enhance quality safety life. There is a statistically significant difference in the prevalence of home accident burns and fractures between male and female geriatric patients. Also, there is a statistical significant relationship between knowledge of the causes of home accident and preventive strategies ($r = .619$, $n = 25$, $p(.001) < .05$). The study recommends implementing regular home safety evaluations for older adults to identify potential hazards and recommend modifications.

Keywords: Home Accidents, Geriatric patients, Burns, Fractures, Injury Prevalence, Elderly Care

Introduction

As the global population ages, the incidence of home accidents, particularly among geriatric patients, has become a growing public health concern. The elderly are more susceptible to home-related injuries due to a combination of factors such as impaired mobility, visual and cognitive deficits, chronic conditions and medication side effects (Ogunrewo, 2020). The incidence of home accidents in older adults is alarmingly high, approximately 30-40% of elderly individuals experience at least one fall annually, with many of these falls resulting in serious injuries (World Health Organisation, 2022). The overall rate of home accidents among the elderly population is increasing, with an

estimated 12-15% of geriatric patients sustaining non-fatal injuries in the home each year (O'Hara *et al* 2024).

The incidence of home accidents is generally higher among individuals over the age of 75 and those with multiple comorbidities, such as diabetes, cardiovascular disease or dementia, notably, the risk of home accidents rises significantly in patients with cognitive impairments, who may be less aware of hazards in their environment and more likely to engage in unsafe behaviors (Olaosebikan, 2023). Falls are the leading cause of home accidents in geriatric patients and are strongly linked to factors such as frailty, osteoporosis, visual impairment and polypharmacy (Smith *et al* 2023). Among the most common injuries reported are burns and fractures, which significantly impact the quality of life of elderly individuals and contribute to an increased healthcare burden (Ogunlesi & Adejumo, 2020). Despite advancements in healthcare, elderly individuals remain disproportionately affected by injuries occurring within the home environment, leading to long-term health complications, diminished quality of life and a significant healthcare burden. Home accidents are a major contributor to hospitalisation and are often exacerbated by age-related physiological and cognitive declines, as well as unsafe living conditions (Lawuyi, 2019).

However, burns and fractures, while less frequently studied, are also substantial causes of morbidity. In most cases, fractures, especially hip fractures, are associated with a high mortality rate and long-term functional impairment in older adults. Similarly, burn injuries in the elderly are often more severe due to delayed medical treatment and complications arising from underlying health conditions such as diabetes or cardiovascular disease (Zhang *et al* 2023). Recent literature highlights the growing concern of these accidents in geriatric patients, with Burns and fractures identified as major contributors to disability and hospital admissions. A report by Olaosebikan. (2023) estimated that the incidence of fractures in older adults could increase by 30% over the next decade, primarily driven by factors such as osteoporosis, decreased mobility and increased environmental hazards in the home. Furthermore, burns, often resulting from exposure to hot liquids or faulty electrical devices, are reported to be more common in individuals with cognitive impairments or diminished sensory abilities (O'Hara *et al* 2024).

Given the rising elderly population and the severity of home accident-related injuries, it is crucial to understand the specific risks and the prevalence of burns and fractures in this demographic. These injuries not only affect the physical health of older individuals but also place a strain on healthcare systems and caregivers. There is an urgent need for targeted interventions, including home safety modifications and preventive measures to reduce the incidence of burns and fractures among geriatric patients (Martin *et al* 2024). Addressing this problem requires both a better understanding of the risk factors and a systematic approach to mitigating these risks in the home setting. While several studies have explored the broader scope of home accidents in the geriatric population, there is limited quantitative data focusing specifically on the incidence rates of burns and fractures. This study aims to fill that gap by quantifying the incidence of home accidents and the prevalence of burns and fractures in a cohort of geriatric patients.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study were to:

1. Investigate the prevalence of home accident burns and fractures among geriatric patients in selected Public Hospitals in Southwest Nigeria.
2. Examine the knowledge of the geriatric patients on the causes of home accident burns and fractures among geriatric patients.
3. Investigate the geriatric patients knowledge of the preventive strategies of home accident burns and fractures among geriatric patients

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant gender difference in the prevalence of home accident burns and fractures among geriatric patients.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between knowledge of the causes of home accident, burns and fractures and preventive strategies among geriatric patients.

Ho₃: There is no significant gender difference in the knowledge of the preventive strategies of home accident burns and fractures among geriatric patients.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopted healthy lifestyle theory, developed primarily by Green & Kreuter in 1999. Healthy lifestyle theory is a comprehensive framework that integrates various aspects of individual behaviours, environmental factors and social influences to promote health and prevent diseases. Healthy lifestyle theory posits that an individual's lifestyle choices—spanning physical activity, nutrition, stress management and health behaviors—are critical determinants of their overall well-being. Healthy lifestyle theory is anchored on the premise that that adopting healthy behaviors can significantly impact individuals' health outcomes and quality of life. It emphasises the interplay between personal choices, environmental factors and social determinants of health. The theory emphasises personal behaviour changes and environmental influences in promoting health and preventing disease. It suggests that adopting a healthy lifestyle involves not only modifying individual behaviours but also making conscious choices regarding one's environment, social support and mental health to maintain overall health and reduce risk factors for diseases and injuries. The theory integrates insights from various disciplines, including psychology, sociology, nutrition science and public health, to create a holistic approach to health promotion and disease prevention. Healthy lifestyle theory represents a proactive approach to healthcare management that emphasises prevention, empowerment and holistic well-being, aligning with the broader goals of public health and healthcare organisations to improve population health and quality of life.

When applied to the incidence of home accidents and the prevalence of burns and fractures among geriatric patients, the healthy lifestyle theory can offer valuable insights into how elderly individuals' behaviors, environment, and social context contribute to these injuries. By fostering healthy lifestyle practices, elderly individuals may reduce their risk of home accidents such as falls and burns, which are common injuries in the geriatric population. This model also emphasises the role of health education, physical

activity, home modifications and social networks in promoting a safer living environment for older adults. The application of the healthy lifestyle theory to geriatric home accidents and injuries can be understood through its four main components, which include health promotion behaviours, environmental and social context, self-efficacy and empowerment and cultural and lifestyle norms. According to the healthy lifestyle theory, the adoption of proactive health behaviors is critical in preventing home accidents and mitigating their severity. For elderly individuals, health-promoting behaviours include physical activity and mobility, injury prevention education, nutritional health. The environmental context of the healthy lifestyle theory emphasises the role of the living environment and social support in shaping health outcomes. In the case of home accidents, environmental modifications and social support systems are key to reducing the risk of injuries such as burns and fractures among the elderly. A key principle of the healthy lifestyle theory is the concept of self-efficacy or an individual's belief in their ability to make positive changes. Empowering elderly individuals to take control of their health and safety is essential to preventing home accidents. The healthy lifestyle theory also considers cultural and lifestyle norms, which can influence health behaviors and attitudes towards safety practices. In geriatric populations, cultural attitudes toward aging, independence and injury prevention can impact the prevalence of home accidents

Adopting a healthy lifestyle that includes physical activity, health education, home safety modifications, and strong social support systems can significantly reduce the risk of home accidents in older adults, improving their overall quality of life and safety. By applying this theory, interventions and public health strategies can be developed to effectively reduce the prevalence of injuries among elderly individuals in home environments.

Methodology

A cross-sectional descriptive design was employed to assess the prevalence of burns and fractures among geriatric patients and explore the contributing factors. Data were collected over a period of six months from selected public hospitals in Southwest Nigeria. The target population for this study includes elderly individuals (aged 65 years and above) who have been treated for home-related accidents, specifically fractures and burns, within the last year. Sample size was determined using the minimum sample size formula for studying simple proportions developed by Cochran (1977). A sample of 134 was used to ensure patients were selected to ensure statistical power and representativeness. The samples were drawn from a combination of urban and rural healthcare settings to ensure diverse representation. Stratified random samplings were used to ensure proportional representation across key variables such as age, gender, comorbidities and cognitive status. Inclusion criteria include adults aged 65 years and older; patients who have been diagnosed with fractures or burns that occurred in the home environment; patients who are either admitted to the hospital or undergoing outpatient rehabilitation services for treatment of these injuries; participants who provide informed consent to participate in the study. While exclusive criteria include patients who sustained fractures or burns from external causes (workplace accidents, vehicular

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accidents); patients less than 65 years of age and individuals with significant cognitive impairments who could not provide informed consent. Questionnaire was used to elicit information on the socio-demographic characteristics and incidence of home accidents (burns and fractures among geriatric patients Data were analysed using descriptive statistics to summarise participant characteristics and incidence of home accidents. Inferential statistics were employed to examine the prevalence, knowledge of the causes and preventive strategies of home accident; specifically, independent t-test, to determine the strength and direction of associations.

Result

The demographic profile of the respondents plays a crucial role in understanding incidence of home accidents and the prevalence of burns and fractures among geriatric patients. Majority of the respondents (84%) are below 85 years of age, with fewer participants in the older age bracket. The distribution indicated a slightly younger geriatric population, with a significant proportion of respondents being under 80. This age distribution also indicated younger elderly patients may have different experiences or risks related to home accidents compared to those in the older age groups. Fractures are significantly more common than burns among the geriatric patients in this study, with nearly two-thirds of the respondents suffering from fractures. Majority of the respondents (80%) suffered from moderate to severe injuries, indicating that a significant portion of geriatric patients are dealing with serious consequences from home accidents. Apart from the demographic findings, there are other major findings.

Table 1: Prevalence of Home Accident Burns and Fractures among Geriatric Patients

Prevalence	Frequency	Percentage
Low	49	28.0
High	85	72.0
Total	134	100

Table 1 indicated that majority of elderly individuals in this group are significantly prone to home-related injuries. This might be that most of them are susceptible to slippery falls due to slippery floor which resulted into fractures.

Table 2: Knowledge the Causes of Home Accident

Knowledge the causes of home accident	Frequency	Percentage
Low	45	33.6
High	89	66.4
Total	134	100

Table 2 indicated that majority of the elderly patients have a good understanding of the factors contributing to home accidents, such as burns and fractures.

Table 3: Knowledge of the Preventive Strategies of Home Accident Burns and Fractures

Knowledge of preventive strategies	Frequency	Percentage
Low	52	39.0
High	82	61.0
Total	134	100

Table 3 indicated that majority of the elderly patients are well-informed about how to prevent such accidents, indicating a positive trend in awareness. This highlights the need for further education to ensure all patients are equipped with the necessary information to minimise the risk of home accidents, particularly burns and fractures, in this vulnerable age group.

Test of Hypotheses

H01: There is no significant prevalence of home accident burns and fractures among geriatric Patients

Table 4: Independent t-test showing the difference in the prevalence of home accident burns and fractures among geriatric.

Prevalence of home accident	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Crit-t	Cal-t.	DF	p value
Male	65	15.4583	2.19237	1.96	-2.182	23	.013
Female	69	19.1154	3.83463				

Table 4 showed that there is a statistically significant difference in the prevalence of home accident burns and fractures between male and female geriatric patients (Crit-t = 1.96, Cal.t = -2.182, DF = 23, p (0.13) <.05 level of significance). Hence, female geriatric patients are prone to home accident, burns and fractures compared to their male counterparts in the study. This finding is buttressed is tangential to Ogunsetan *et al's* (2021) assertion that when it comes to fractures, studies consistently show that elderly women have a higher prevalence of hip fractures, primarily due to osteoporosis. The hypothesis is, therefore, rejected.

H02: There is no significant relationship between knowledge of the causes of home accident, burns and fractures and preventive strategies among geriatric patients

Table 5: Independent t-test showing the difference in the knowledge of the preventive strategies of home accident, burns, and fractures between male and female geriatrics patients

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	r	p-value	Remarks
Knowledge of the causes	18.8000	3.84520	25	.619*	.001	Sig.
Preventive strategies	14.2400	2.3516				

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 showed that there is a statistical significant relationship between knowledge of the causes of home accident and preventive strategies ($r = .619$, $n = 25$, $p(.001) < .05$). Hence, knowledge of the causes of home accident, burns, and fractures influenced/enhanced the preventive strategies deployed by geriatrics patients in the study. The hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Ho₃: There is no significant gender difference in the knowledge of the preventive strategies of home accident burns and fractures among geriatric patients

Table 6: Independent t-test showing the difference in the knowledge of the preventive strategies of home accident, burns, and fractures between male and female geriatrics patients

Knowledge of the preventive strategies	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Crit-t	Cal-t.	DF	p value
Male	65	13.5000	2.12461	1.96	-0.189	23	.852
Female	69	14.9231	2.53312				

Source: 2024 Field Survey

Table 6 showed that there is no statistically significant difference in the knowledge of the preventive strategies of home accident, burns, and fractures between male and female geriatrics (Crit-t = 1.96, Cal.t = -0.189, DF = 23, $p(0.852) > .05$ level of significance). Hence, knowledge of the preventive strategies of home accident burns and fractures among geriatric patients is the same regardless of the gender in the study. This finding also in line with McMahon *et al* (2018) that both male and female participants demonstrated comparable levels of understanding regarding risk factors and preventive measures, such as home modifications and physical exercises aimed at reducing falls. Hence, the hypothesis is therefore accepted.

Discussions of Findings

The prevalence of home accidents (fractures and burns) is high in the study areas as majority of elderly individuals are significantly prone to home-related injuries. This finding is in line with assertion of Olaosebikan *et al* (2023) that older adults have a higher mortality rate from fractures and burns compared to younger populations. Slippery floor has the highest percentage out the predominant sources of geriatric patients home accidents, corroborates the findings of Owoaje *et al* (2015) that falls are one of the most frequent causes of injuries among elderly people. He reported that falls accounted for approximately 40% of all injuries among elderly people. The finding is also in line with the study of O’Hara *et al* (2024) that slips and falls are among the most common types of accidents in the home, with a significant proportion of these incidents involving old people. Age-related physiological changes, such as decreased bone density, muscle mass, and skin elasticity, play a major role in making older adults more vulnerable to these types of injuries (Smith *et al* 2023). Cognitive decline and dementia further increase the

risk, as these conditions impair judgement and decrease the ability to avoid hazardous situations.

When it comes to fractures, studies consistently show that elderly women have a higher prevalence of hip fractures, primarily due to osteoporosis. According to Kelsey *et al* (2017), women over 65 years of age are four times more likely to sustain hip fractures compared to men. This increased risk is attributed to lower bone density and the hormonal changes associated with menopause.

This study indicated that majority of the elderly patients have a good understanding of the factors contributing to home accidents, such as burns and fractures and also the preventive strategies yet many older people fall victims.. However, extant studies have shown that that many elderly individuals possess some knowledge of strategies to prevent home-related injuries, yet gaps remain. Bamisaye *et al* (2023) found that approximately 65% of older adults recognised the importance of using assistive devices yet still lacks some appropriate home modifications. This finding is also in line with Olajde *et al* (2020) who found that 78% of older adults recognised environmental hazards, such as poor lighting and clutter, as significant risk factors for falls. This awareness was linked to previous experiences with falls or injuries, suggesting that personal experience enhances knowledge. Despite a generally high level of awareness, barriers still exist that can hinder elderly individuals from effectively translating knowledge into practice. There is need tailoring educational materials to meet the specific needs of this demographic, considering their unique challenges.

The finding that there is a statistically significant difference in the prevalence of home accident female geriatric patients are prone to home accident, burns, and fractures compared to their male counterparts fractures, is in line with the finding of Baker *et al* (2019) that men aged 65 and older had a 30% higher rate of burn injuries than women in the same age group. The authors attributed this discrepancy to factors such as increased risk-taking behavior and higher exposure to hazardous activities like cooking or using hot liquids.

The finding that there is a statistical significant relationship between knowledge of the causes of home accident and preventive strategies, is in line with the finding of Ojifinmi *et al* (2015) that increased awareness of common causes of home injuries (like drowning and falls) led to a greater implementation of safety measures, such as installing gates and using pool covers. The researchers concluded that educational interventions focusing on risk factors significantly influenced caregivers' behaviours, thereby reducing injury rates.

The finding that there is no statistically significant gender difference in the knowledge of the preventive strategies; and Knowledge of the preventive strategies of home accident burns and fractures among geriatric patients is the same regardless of the gender, is in line with the finding of a study conducted by Sridharan *et al* (2016) that focused on the knowledge of various home accident prevention strategies, including those related to burns and fractures. Their findings revealed that there were no significant differences between male and female older adults in understanding how to prevent these accidents. Both genders reported similar awareness of the importance of environmental

modifications, such as improving lighting and removing tripping hazards. The findings from this study have significant implications for healthcare providers, policymakers, and the wider community. These implications are informed by incidence of Home accidents and the Prevalence of Burns and Fractures among Geriatric patients. The study recommends implementing regular home safety evaluations for older adults to identify potential hazards and recommend modifications, such as installing grab bars, improving lighting, and removing tripping hazards

Conclusion

The investigation into the incidence of home accidents and the prevalence of burns and fractures among geriatric patients revealed critical insights into the safety challenges faced by this vulnerable population. The findings underscored that older adults are at heightened risk for home-related injuries, particularly due to factors such as physical frailty, cognitive decline and unsafe living environments. The high rates of burns and fractures, primarily resulting from falls and kitchen-related incidents, highlight the urgent need for targeted prevention strategies. These may include comprehensive home safety assessments, community education programs, and the promotion of assistive devices to enhance mobility and reduce hazards. Moreover, this study emphasises the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration among healthcare providers, caregivers and community organisations to create a supportive network that addresses the unique needs of geriatric patients. By implementing proactive measures and fostering awareness, we can significantly decrease the incidence of home accidents, thereby improving the overall quality of life for older adults. Addressing the factors contributing to home accidents is essential for enhancing safety and well-being in the geriatric population. Ongoing research and policy efforts are vital to ensure that older adults can live independently and safely in their homes. Thus, the following recommendations are hereby given:

1. Develop targeted educational initiatives for both geriatric patients and their caregivers, focusing on safety practices in the home, including cooking safety to prevent burns and strategies to reduce fall risks.
2. Advocate for policies that promote funding for home modifications and safety programmes aimed at reducing accidents among older adults. This includes support for initiatives that provide resources for low-income families.
3. Launch community-wide awareness campaigns aimed at educating families and caregivers about the risks of home accidents among older adults and the importance of preventive measures.

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